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3 1 **Relative Susceptibility of New Olive Cultivars to *Spilocaea oleagina*, *Colletotrichum***
4 ***acutatum*, and *Pseudocercospora cladosporioides***
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16 **ABSTRACT**

17 Moral, J., Alsalimiya, M., Roca, L. F., Díez, M. C., León, L., de la Rosa, R., Barranco,
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22 The evaluation of the relative susceptibility of new cultivars to the main diseases of a
23 crop is a key point to consider prior to their release to the nursery industry. This study
24 provides a rigorous characterization of the resistance of 15 new olive cultivars and their
25 genitors ('Arbequina', 'Frantoio', and 'Picual') to the three main aerial diseases:
26 peacock spot, anthracnose, and cercosporiose caused by *Spilocaea oleagina*,
27 *Colletotrichum acutatum*, and *Pseudocercospora cladosporioides*, respectively. To do
28 so, developing leaves and detached green-yellowish fruit were inoculated in laboratory
29 tests with *S. oleagina* and *C. acutatum*, respectively, using conidial suspensions of both
30 pathogens. Additionally, a previously validated rating scale was used to assess the
31 incidence of leaves with symptoms of *S. oleagina* or *P. cladosporioides* and the rot-fruit
32 incidence of *C. acutatum* in the trees for four years under field conditions. As a result,

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1 only two of the cultivars were susceptible to peacock spot, most likely because these
2 new cultivars were previously screened for resistance to the disease on previous phases
3 of the breeding program. Conversely, the 15 cultivars were susceptible or moderately
4 susceptible to cercosporiose. Five of the 15 new cultivars were classified as resistant to
5 anthracnose, with four of them descendants of 'Frantoio' × 'Picual' crosses. In
6 addition, the cultivar resistance to *C. acutatum* showed a negative linear correlation
7 with the total phenols content of olive oil. This information regarding disease reaction
8 of the new olive cultivars is essential for nursery industry and growers.

9 *Additional keywords: Fusicladium oleagineum, Olea europaea, soapy rot*

11
12 Foliar and fruit fungal pathogens cause economically important diseases in olives (*Olea*
13 *europaea* L.) in most olive-growing areas around the world (8,41,42). Within these
14 pathogens, the most serious diseases in order of importance are peacock spot,
15 anthracnose, and cercosporiose caused by *Spilocaea oleagina*, *Colletotrichum* spp., and
16 *Pseudocercospora cladosporioides*, respectively (42). These pathogens cause tree
17 defoliation, branch dieback, premature fruit dropping and fruit rot, which can devastate
18 entire olive production under pathogen-favoring environmental conditions (8,32,42). In
19 addition, the olive oil quality is also affected by these pathogens, particularly
20 *Colletotrichum* spp. The olive oils from fruit that are affected by *Colletotrichum* spp.
21 show low oxidative stability and polyphenol and α -tocopherol content and various
22 organoleptic defects (33). In Spain, the overall loss in net income for the olive industry
23 due to these three diseases is approximately \$315 million per annum (8,32).

24 The management of aerial olive diseases in the field involves cultural and chemical
25 practices, including preventive sprays with copper-based fungicides (8,41). The
26 commercial control of aerial olive diseases requires 2-6 fungicide applications during
27 the entire growth season, although a higher number of applications could be necessary
28 in wet areas, in areas of super-high-density planting (hedgerow orchards), or when
29 susceptible cultivars are grown (25).

30 Successful olive breeding programs by crossing and progeny selection began in various
31 countries at the end of the 1980s (5,15). In Spain, a breeding program to obtain new
32 cultivars for oil production began in 1991 in Córdoba Province (Andalusian region,
33 Southern Spain). Since then, more than 10,000 seedlings from open and controlled
34 crosses between traditional cultivars have been screened and selected as new cultivars

1 according to two main features: first, desirable agronomical traits, such as low tree vigor
2 and exceptional oil quality profiles (11,16,17,33,37,38); and second, disease resistance,
3 which offers an economically sound alternative to chemical control (1,23,33). To this
4 end, we evaluated the relative susceptibility of new cultivars to peacock spot,
5 anthracnose, and cercosporiose, which were systematically evaluated under field and
6 controlled conditions. Field evaluations were conducted for several seasons because the
7 severity of these diseases depends on the specific weather conditions of each year
8 (2,25). Moreover, severe epidemics are necessary for a correct classification of the
9 susceptibility of olive cultivars to allow the observation of the complete range of olive
10 resistance in the field (23). These long-term field evaluations also allow us to describe
11 the susceptibility of the new cultivars to other more sporadic diseases. For example, the
12 olive cv. FS-17 is unusually susceptible to *Alternaria alternata* (28), and the cv. Barnea
13 is extremely susceptible to olive knot caused by the bacterium *Pseudomonas savastanoi*
14 pv. *savastanoi* under field conditions (24). Additionally, the relative susceptibility of
15 new olive cultivars to these pathogens should be confirmed by artificial inoculation
16 because the olive tree frequently avoids these pathogens under field conditions (27,45).

17 Olive fruit and, by extension, olive oils are highly rich in polyphenols, which are of
18 significant physiological importance for both the plants and their human consumers
19 (4,11). Phenolic compounds from olive may inhibit the growth of pathogens, such as *S.*
20 *oleagina* (13) and species of genera *Phytophthora* and *Cylindrocarpon* (3,10). In
21 addition, these compounds show a preventive role in olive fly (*Bactrocera oleae*)
22 infestations (47). The greater susceptibility to *Colletotrichum* spp. of mature olive fruit
23 may be related to the loss of one or several host resistance mechanisms that are present
24 in immature fruit, including decreases or changes in the phenolic compounds (27,35).
25 The relationship between phenolic compounds and olive resistance to *Colletotrichum* is
26 unknown.

27 This study evaluates the phenotypic expression of resistance of 15 new olive cultivars
28 and their genitors ('Arbequina', 'Frantoio', and 'Picual') to three major aerial pathogens
29 of olive, *S. oleagina*, *C. acutatum*, and *P. cladosporioides*. We evaluated the incidence
30 of leaves and fruit that were affected by the pathogens for four seasons in an
31 experimental orchard where the three diseases are endemic. In addition, standard
32 inoculation tests were performed under controlled conditions. Finally, we establish the

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1 relationship between the phenols of olive oil and the resistance of olive fruit to
2 *Colletotrichum*.

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

4 **Plant material.** The 15 evaluated genotypes are new cultivars from the first set of 748
5 seedlings from reciprocal crosses among the cvs. Arbequina, Frantoio, and Picual that
6 were conducted by the Agronomy Department of the University of Córdoba and the
7 Andalusian Institute for Research and Formation in Agriculture and Fishery (IFAPA in
8 Spanish) in Córdoba during the springs of 1991 and 1992 (36,38). The results from
9 previous studies regarding the productivity, fruit characteristics (i.e., removal force,
10 size, and ripening time) and olive oil (i.e., fatty acid composition and phenolic profile)
11 characteristics of these and additional genotypes have been reported (9,11,16,17). The
12 15 new cultivars and their genitors, which were used as controls, were vegetatively
13 propagated (rooted semi-hardwood stem cutting) and planted in the field in July 2001
14 (Table 1). The experimental orchard was located in a 1.2-ha flat, uniform field at the
15 IFAPA Alameda del Obispo Agricultural Research Station, Córdoba, Southern Spain
16 (37.5°N, 4.8°W, altitude 110 m). The soil of the orchard was classified as a Typic
17 Xerofluvent with a sandy-loam texture, and the climatic conditions were typical of the
18 Mediterranean area. The experimental orchard is located 703 m from the main river of
19 Andalucía, Guadalquivir River, in a humid area where anthracnose, peacock spot, and
20 cercosporiose are endemic diseases. Initially, a randomized block design with 16
21 replications and one tree per plot was used with a 5 m distance between olive trees in a
22 row and 6 m between rows. Currently, only 10 blocks remain due to the removal of six
23 blocks for road construction. Due to the rabbits, however, there was one tree less of the
24 cvs. Picual, UC-I 7-34, and UC-I 7-60. The trees in the orchard were drip-irrigated, and
25 the experimental orchard was managed as per the principles of commercial olive
26 orchards in Andalusia (4). Copper-based fungicides (copper sulfate, 3.5 kg Cu per ha)
27 were applied during the spring and autumn to semi-control the fungal foliar and fruit
28 diseases (42). No fungicide treatments, however, were applied to allow for the
29 development of an anthracnose epidemic in 2011.

30 The relative susceptibility of the genitors to *S. oleagina*, *C. acutatum*, and *P.*
31 *cladosporioides* was previously characterized as follows: cv. Frantoio is resistant (R),
32 resistant (R), and susceptible (S), respectively; cv. Picual is susceptible (S), resistant

1 (R), and moderately susceptible (M), respectively; and cv. Arbequina is moderately
2 susceptible (M) to the three pathogens (2,23,43; Table 2). The three genitors were used
3 as controls in both the field and controlled trials.

4 **Susceptibility of the new cultivars in artificial inoculations.** The relative
5 susceptibility to peacock spot and anthracnose of the 15 new cultivars was evaluated
6 under controlled conditions. The relative susceptibility to cercosporiose was not
7 evaluated because the long incubation period of the disease (up to 18 months) does not
8 allow for differentiating the infected leaves from those with natural senescence
9 symptoms (2).

10 *Spilocaea oleagina*. Developing leaves of the 15 new cultivars were collected from the
11 trees in the experimental orchard during the spring of 2003. The detached leaves were
12 placed in plastic trays between two layers of moistened filter paper immediately after
13 the leaves were removed from the plants. Before inoculation, the detached leaves were
14 preconditioned for 24 h at the same temperature to which they would be exposed after
15 inoculation. The inoculum was obtained from naturally infected leaves with sporulating
16 peacock spot lesions that were collected from December-March (45). The affected olive
17 leaves of cv. Manzanilla de Antequera located in Málaga Province (Andalucía region)
18 were used as the inoculum source. The detached leaves were sprayed with a conidial
19 suspension of 10^5 conidia per ml or sterile water for the control and incubated as
20 described in the previous section. The inoculated and control leaves were assessed for
21 disease severity 50 days after inoculation. To reveal the latent infections, we immersed
22 the inoculated leaves in a 5% sodium hydroxide solution for 30 min at room
23 temperature ($22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$). After this treatment, the visible lesions were more prominent,
24 and the latent infections appeared as black circular spots or rings, clearly differentiated
25 from the healthy green tissue (46). Disease severity was assessed using a 0-to-8 rating
26 scale. The scale considers the percentage of the affected leaf surface similar to the rating
27 scale of Viruega *et al.* (45): 0 = no symptoms, 1 = < 12.5%, 2 = 12.5-25%, 4 = 26-50%,
28 6 = 51-75%, and 8 = > 75% of the upper surface covered by black spots lesions. The
29 evaluators were trained using the software ASSESS (14) to obtain a good relationship
30 between the scale value and the pathogen-affected leaf surface. The disease severity
31 index (DSI) was calculated in each replication and was expressed as the relative severity
32 with respect to the susceptible parent cv. Picual. There were three replicates (moist
33 chambers) per treatment with 20 leaves per replicate arranged in a completely

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1 randomized design. The experiment was repeated twice using two populations of the
2 pathogen from different orchards.

3 *Colletotrichum acutatum*. Olive fruit from the 15 new cultivars were collected at the
4 onset of ripening from trees in the experimental orchard in 2005. The fruit were green-
5 yellowish and had a value of 1 on the 0-(green fruit)-to-4-(black fruit) ripening scale
6 (4). The fruit were washed, disinfested, air-dried, and sprayed with a conidial
7 suspension (10^5 conidia per ml or sterile water for the control) from pure cultures of the
8 pathogen on agar potato dextrose (PDA) as described by Moral *et al.* (27). To assure
9 that the conidia were viable; we evaluated their germination, which ranged from 50 to
10 80%. The inoculated and control fruit were incubated in moist chambers (plastic
11 containers, $22 \times 16 \times 10$ cm with 100% RH) at $23 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ under fluorescent lights (12-h
12 photoperiod, $350 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). The disease severity was assessed weekly for one month
13 after inoculation using a 0-to-5 rating scale where 0 = no visible symptoms, 1 = visible
14 symptoms affecting less than 25% of the fruit surface, 2 = 25 to 50%, 3 = 50 to 75%, 4
15 = 75 to 100%, and 5 = fruit completely rotted (soapy fruit) with abundant conidia in a
16 gelatinous matrix. A disease severity index (DSI) was calculated for each replication
17 using the following formula: $DSI = (\sum n_i \times i) / N$, where I represents severity (0 to 5), n_i is
18 the number of fruits with a severity of i , and N is the total number of fruit (27). The area
19 under the disease progress curve (AUDPC) was calculated via the trapezoidal
20 integration of DSI values over time. There were three replicates (moist chambers) per
21 treatment with 25 fruit per replicate arranged in a completely randomized design. The
22 experiment was repeated twice using the isolates Col-87 and Col-94. Both of the
23 isolates were identified as *C. acutatum*-group A4 according to their internally
24 transcribed spacer 5.8S and β -tubulin regions. According to Damm *et al.* (7), group A4
25 corresponds to *C. godetiae*, although the latter name is rarely used. The *C. acutatum*
26 group A4 is the dominant group in the Andalusia region (33) and is the only isolated
27 that was detected in the experimental orchard.

28 **Susceptibility of the new cultivars under field conditions.** The disease severity of
29 anthracnose, peacock spot, and cercosporiose was assessed in each olive tree by
30 estimating the percentage of affected fruit or leaves, using a 0-to-10 rating scale where 0
31 = no affected fruits or leaves per tree, 1 = one to three affected fruits or leaves per tree,
32 and 2 = one to three affected fruits or leaves per each quadrant of the tree canopy.
33 Higher rating values were obtained by directly estimating the percentage of affected

1 leaves or fruit with 5 = 10, 6 = 25, 7 = 50, 8 = 75, 9 = 90, and 10 = > 94% of the
2 affected tissues. Then, the data of the percentage affected leaves or fruits were
3 transformed in scaling rating values using the logistic equation (23):

$$4 \text{ Logit (Y)} = \text{Ln} \frac{Y}{100 - Y} = -1.2 \times (X - 7) \quad (1)$$

5 where X is the scaling rating value, and Y is the percentage of affected leaves or fruit.
6 The transformed scale data are normally distributed so that they can be directly
7 subjected to an analysis of variance and other parametric analyses. This rating scale is a
8 useful and rapid method to estimate the incidence of affected leaves or fruit in a tree
9 based on the binary nature of the data and the logistic growth of the epidemics (23).

10 During the disease evaluations, the assessors circled the canopy of each olive tree
11 looking for affected leaves or fruit in a 1-to-2-m band above ground. The area checked
12 was approximately 1/4 (25%) of the total canopy. The assessment took approximately 3
13 to 10 min, depending on the size of the olive canopy. Overall, the incidence of fruit with
14 symptoms of anthracnose or leaves with symptoms of cercosporiose or peacock spot
15 were assessed while these tissues were still attached to the tree, but in some cases, the
16 assessment included the fruit or leaves on the soil surface. With cercosporiose, both the
17 upper and lower surfaces of the leaves were observed because the pathogen, at times,
18 sporulated abundantly on the lower surface of the asymptomatic leaves. Conversely, the
19 chlorotic leaves without signs of pathogen infection were incubated in a humid chamber
20 for 14 days to induce fungal sporulation and to avoid confusion with the senescent
21 leaves. For every disease, each tree was rated by two people, and the means were
22 calculated from all of the ratings. The evaluations were carried out from 2006 to 2011
23 from December-March.

24 **Relationship between the phenolic content and fruit resistance to *Colletotrichum*.**

25 To study the relationship between the phenolic compounds of fruit and the anthracnose
26 resistance of genotypes, we used the recently published data of the phenolic profile of
27 olive oil from nine of the new cultivars and the three genitors (11). These authors (11)
28 collected olive fruit in 2009, a non-epidemic year, and characterized the phenolic profile
29 of the oil of each cultivar by liquid-liquid extraction with 60:40 (v/v) methanol-water
30 and subsequent chromatographic analysis with absorption and fluorescent detection in a
31 sequential configuration. In this study, the concentration of the following compounds

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1 was determined: apigenin, hydroxyl-tyrosol, luteolin, *p*-Coumaric acid, *o*-Coumaric
2 acid, tyrosol, vanillic acid, 3,4-DHPEA-EDA (dialdehydic form of elenolic acid linked
3 to hydroxytyrosol), and total phenols. Because the phenolic profile of olive oil was
4 determined for each cultivar and ripening scale value from 0-(green fruit)-to-4-(black
5 fruit), we correlated the total or specific phenol contents of the oils from fruits on each
6 ripening scale value with the severity of the symptoms (AUDPC). In addition, we used
7 the average total or specific phenol contents of the oil for this correlation.

8 **Data Analysis.** The data analysis was performed using Statistix software (version 10;
9 Statistix, Tallahassee, FL). In the inoculation experiments, the effects of the olive
10 genotype on anthracnose and peacock spot severity were determined by an analysis of
11 variance (ANOVA) because these data satisfied the normality and homogeneity of the
12 variance requirements of ANOVA. The *C. acutatum* isolate or *S. oleagina* pathogen
13 population was used as a block because the effects of the isolate or pathogen population
14 and its interaction with the olive genotype were not significant ($P > 0.05$). The
15 relationship between anthracnose severity (AUDPC) and the concentration of each
16 phenolic compound of olive oil was analyzed by Pearson's correlation test and then by
17 linear regression analysis.

18 In the field experiments, the ANOVA was performed on the rating scale data of fruit-rot
19 incidence and incidence of infected leaves for each year due to the important differences
20 among the years. When none of the trees of the same cultivar showed any disease
21 symptoms, the cultivar was considered significantly different from the diseased
22 cultivars. Dunnett's test was used to determine the significant differences between each
23 genotype and the cultivar control ('Arbequina') at $P < 0.05$. The parental 'Arbequina'
24 was selected as the control because it is moderately susceptible to the three pathogens
25 and enables the separation of the genotypes, such as resistant, moderately susceptible, or
26 susceptible. The relationship between the average rating scale data under field
27 conditions and the severity under artificial inoculations was studied using a linear
28 regression analysis forced through the origin. Finally, the relationship among the
29 resistance to the three pathogens of the olive genotypes was studied by Pearson
30 correlation.

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RESULTS

Susceptibility of the new olive cultivars to artificial inoculations.

Spilocaea oleagina. All of the genotypes showed latent or visible symptoms of peacock spot 50 days after inoculation. The DSI varied among the new cultivars ($P < 0.001$), whereas the population of the pathogen and its interaction with the genotype were not significant ($P > 0.05$). Among the genitors, the cv. Picual was the most susceptible to the pathogen, and the cv. Frantoio was the most resistant. The DSI of the new cultivars ranged from 15.13% for UC-I 1-19 to 96.36% for UC-I 10-54. No other genotype was as resistant to the pathogen as was the cv. Frantoio. Five new cultivars were significantly ($P > 0.05$) more resistant to *S. oleagina* than was the cv. Arbequina, while UC-I 10-54 as susceptible as cv. Picual. The other genotypes did not differ significantly ($P > 0.05$) in susceptibility compared the control cultivar. Three out of five resistant new cultivars descended from the 'Frantoio' × 'Picual' crosses (Fig. 1).

Colletotrichum acutatum. All of the genotypes developed fruit rot symptoms by the end of the experiment 28 days after inoculation. Cultivar Frantoio, however, showed only two fruit (1.3%) with anthracnose symptoms 28 days after inoculation, but 60 days after inoculation 40% of the fruit exhibited disease symptoms. The disease severity (AUDPC) varied greatly among the genotypes ($P < 0.001$) but the effect of isolates and the genotype-isolate interaction did not significantly influence the disease severity ($P > 0.05$). The genitors exhibited different responses to *C. acutatum*, with the cvs. Frantoio and Picual being more resistant than the cv. Arbequina. Four of the 15 new cultivars were significantly ($P < 0.05$) more susceptible to *C. acutatum* than the cv. Arbequina, while another four were as susceptible as this cultivar. Conversely, seven new cultivars were more resistant than the cv. Arbequina, with four descending from 'Frantoio' × 'Picual' crosses (Fig. 2).

Susceptibility of the new cultivars under field conditions. The leaves affected by *S. oleagina* or *P. cladosporioides* and the incidence of fruit with symptoms of *C. acutatum* in the new cultivars and their genitors varied greatly among years and genotypes (Table 1). During the 4 years of this study (2007, 2008, 2010, and 2011), two years (2007 and 2011) were favorable for peacock spot epidemics, other two years (2010 and 2011) were favorable for cercosporiose epidemics, and only one year (2011) was favorable for anthracnose epidemics. However, some trees of the new cultivars UC-I 8-20 and UC-I

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1 9-67 and the cvs. Chiquitita and Arbequina showed a small number of infected fruits in
2 previous seasons. During the favorable years for peacock spot epidemics, nine new
3 cultivars were significantly ($P < 0.05$) more resistant to *S. oleagina* than was the cv.
4 Arbequina, four new cultivars showed a similar disease incidence, and only the new
5 cultivars UC-I 4-62 and UC-I 10-54 were more susceptible to *S. oleagina* than cv.
6 Arbequina (Table 1). The latter two new cultivars were even more susceptible to
7 peacock spot than the susceptible genitor Picual (*data not shown*), although this cultivar
8 did not differ significantly from the moderately susceptible cv. Arbequina in these
9 experiments.

10 With regard to cercosporiose, the genitors 'Frantoio' and 'Picual' and all new cultivars
11 were equally or more susceptible than cv. Arbequina. When considering only the most
12 favorable year (2011), nine and six of the new cultivars were respectively more or
13 equally susceptible to *P. cladosporioides* than this control cultivar (Table 1). In 2007
14 and 2011, the high susceptibility of UC-I 10-54 to peacock spot hindered the correct
15 evaluation of the severity of *P. cladosporioides*, because most of leaf surface was
16 affected by *S. oleagina*.

17 Under field conditions, none of the new cultivars were more susceptible to *C. acutatum*
18 than was the cv. Arbequina; seven were more resistant to the disease than was the cv.
19 Arbequina, and the remaining showed a range of resistance that was similar to that of
20 this cultivar (Table 1).

21 The disease severity based on both artificial inoculation and field observations for the
22 15 new cultivars and their genitors were compared by linear regression analysis. With
23 peacock spot, a good linear regression ($Y = 0.04X$; $R^2 = 0.677$; and $P < 0.001$) between
24 the susceptibility of new cultivars and their genitors under artificial and field conditions
25 was observed (Fig. 3). In the case of peacock spot, this relationship was highly accurate
26 ($Y = 0.10X$; $R^2 = 0.855$; and $P < 0.001$) (Fig.4).

27 Finally, when the correlations among the susceptibility of the olive genotypes to the
28 three diseases were studied, we only observed a low but significant correlation ($r =$
29 0.481 ; $P = 0.043$) among the resistance to peacock spot and anthracnose.

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1 Relationship between phenolic content and resistance to *Colletotrichum*.

2 The phenolic composition and the total phenol content varied greatly among the 12
3 studied cultivars. The higher of phenol content was obtained from the cv. Frantoio [598
4 mg gallic acid equivalent (GAE) kg⁻¹ oil]. Conversely, the olive oil of the cv. UC-I 9-67
5 showed the lowest total phenol content (132 GAE kg⁻¹ oil). The anthracnose severity
6 (AUDPC) of the inoculated fruit showed negative linear correlations ($R^2 > 0.500$; $P <$
7 0.05) with the total phenol content of oil from the fruits in each ripening scale value.
8 This correlation showed the best fit ($R^2 = 0.580$; $P = 0.004$) when we used the phenolic
9 content of olive oil from the green-yellowish fruit of each cultivar (Fig. 5), coinciding
10 with the inoculation ripening stage of the inoculated fruit. Conversely, the disease
11 severity was not correlated (Pearson correlation; $r > 0.05$) with any of the eight
12 (apigenin, hydroxyl-tyrosol, luteolin, *p*-Coumaric acid, *o*-Coumaric acid, tyrosol,
13 vanillic acid, and 3,4-DHPEA-EDA) specific phenols of olive oil.

14 DISCUSSION

15 We evaluated the response of 15 new olive cultivars to the main aerial olive pathogens
16 *S. oleagina*, *C. acutatum*, and *P. cladosporioides* under field and controlled conditions.
17 As a result, we found wide variability in the response of the cultivars to the diseases,
18 ranging from resistant to very susceptible. This large variation agrees with the
19 variability that has been found for other horticultural characteristics, such as yield per
20 tree, ripening date, and oil content (9,16,17). This diverse response might be due to the
21 different agronomical performances of the genitors (cvs. Arbequina, Frantoio and
22 Picual) to these diseases (1,2,23,26). Additionally, the generally high heterozygosity
23 that is exhibited by olive cultivars may explain the broad segregation that is observed in
24 their offspring (36,38).

25 The relative susceptibility to *S. oleagina* and *C. acutatum* was tested under field and
26 controlled conditions using inoculation methods that were previously applied to assess
27 cultivar resistance (18,19,23), pathogenic variability of fungi (18,30), and efficacy of
28 biological and chemical control products (39). The relative susceptibility to *P.*
29 *cladosporioides* was evaluated only under field conditions due to the pathogen showing
30 more than one year of latency. This feature does not allow for the differentiation
31 between the infected leaves and those with natural senescence symptoms (2). Field

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1 evaluations were carried out for four years using a previously validated rating scale
2 (23).

3 Resistance and susceptibility are two extremes of a continuum of olive reactions to
4 aerial fungal diseases (24); consequently, olive reactions do not separate into discrete
5 categories (6,26). Nevertheless, descriptions and comparisons of cultivars are more
6 pragmatic and easily understood if the disease reactions are placed into distinct ordinal
7 classes (34). To this end, olive cultivar reactions are often grouped into three or five
8 groups from resistant to susceptible based on the severity of the disease symptoms
9 (1,2,23,26,43). In this study, the new cultivars were compared with the genitor
10 'Arbequina', which has been extensively studied and is considered moderately
11 susceptible to the three pathogens (2,23,26,43). The genotypes were classified as
12 resistant, moderately susceptible, or susceptible when they were respectively less,
13 equally, or more susceptible to a pathogen than was the control cultivar. Several new
14 cultivars were classified for their resistance to *S. oleagina* or *C. acutatum* into two
15 different resistance groups depending on field or controlled trial, although none of them
16 showed the opposite reaction (i.e., R and S or S and R) in both trials (Table 2). Because
17 the resistance to anthracnose and peacock spot is correlated with the used genitor
18 'Frantoio' (23,26,43), this correlation was also observed with the new cultivars.

19 Based on the combined laboratory and field evaluations, 14 new cultivars were
20 classified as resistant or moderately susceptible to *S. oleagina*. Only the cv. UC-I 10-54
21 was classified as susceptible to peacock spot. This high proportion of resistant
22 genotypes could be explained by the early screening test for peacock spot resistance that
23 is applied to seedlings in this olive breeding program (1,26,36,38). This test takes
24 advantage of the strong correlation between the resistance to *S. oleagina* of seedlings
25 and that of adult plants, although some susceptible seedlings might escape this
26 screening, such as the new cultivars UC-I 4-62 and UC-I 10-54 (1,14). The latter
27 cultivar was extremely susceptible to *S. oleagina* under field conditions, showing a
28 heavy defoliation (average severity = 7.85) even with the weather conditions of the year
29 being unfavorable for the disease. Under the same conditions, the infected trees of the
30 susceptible parental 'Picual' showed slight defoliation (average severity = 2.92). For
31 this unusual susceptibility, the cv. UC-I 10-54 is currently being used to study the
32 influence of several factors on leaf infection caused by *S. oleagina*.

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3 1 Four of the 15 new genotypes (cvs. Chiquitita, UC-I 2-68, UC-I 8-20, and UC-I 11-10)
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5 2 were susceptible to *C. acutatum* in the controlled inoculations. The other 11 new
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7 3 cultivars were classified as resistant or moderately susceptible to this pathogen. Under
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9 4 field conditions, there was only an anthracnose epidemic during the fall-winter of 2011,
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11 5 and no cultivar was more susceptible to *C. acutatum* than was the cv. Arbequina. This
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13 6 overall resistance could be due to the resistance of two of the genitors, the cvs. Frantoio
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15 7 and Picual (23,26). The weather conditions of each season strongly influenced the
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17 8 development of anthracnose highlighting the necessity to evaluate the disease resistance
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19 9 for several years (23). Remarkably, there was a good correlation between the reactions
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21 10 of the genotypes under the controlled and field conditions as has been previously
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23 11 reported (23). The selection of new genotypes with an elevated resistance to *C.*
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25 12 *acutatum* is essential because (i) diseased fruit, even with a low incidence, adversely
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27 13 affect the quality of the olive oil (33); (ii) fungicides have a limited use because *C.*
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29 14 *acutatum* has low sensitivity to copper fungicides, and the use of organic fungicides in
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31 15 olive orchards is very scarce (39,40); and (iii) the disease is particularly severe in
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33 16 orchards that are densely planted, such as new super-intensive olive growing systems
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35 17 (29). In addition, several fruit of the cvs. UC-I 9-67 and UC-I 0-54 were affected by
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37 18 *Botryosphaeria dothidea*, the causal agent of dalmatian disease (31), while *Phlyctema*
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39 19 *vagabunda*, the causal agent of fruit leprosy (42), affected the fruits of the cv. UC-I 4-62
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41 20 in the field. These diseases, however, have not been extensively evaluated because they
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43 21 were not homogeneously distributed in the orchard and affected only some of the
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45 22 cultivars and trees.

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47 23 Some studies support the idea that the resistance to pathogens and pests might be related
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49 24 to certain types of phenolics of olive tissues (3,10,13,47), but data are often lacking for
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51 25 olive anthracnose. To establish this relationship, we used the phenolic profile of olive
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53 26 oil from the same cultivars of our study, which were recently published (11). Our results
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55 27 showed that the resistance of olive fruit to *Colletotrichum* spp. is related to the
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57 28 constitutive phenolic content of fruit, similar to other diseases that are caused by this
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59 29 pathogen (21,22). Conversely, Gomes et al. (12) did not find a relationship between the
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61 30 total phenolic compounds of olive fruits of the cvs. Galega vulgar and Cobrançosa and
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63 31 resistance to *Colletotrichum*, although this can be explained by the fact that both
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65 32 cultivars are highly and moderately susceptible to the pathogen, respectively (33). Olive
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67 33 fruit susceptibility increases with increasing fruit maturity (27), which in turn decreases

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1 the total phenol content (11,40). In olive anthracnose, previous studies carried out on
2 the antifungal properties of extracts from the exocarp and mesocarp of unripened fruit
3 of the susceptible cv. Barnea indicated that the main antifungal compounds that are
4 present in unripened fruit are phenolics (J. Moral, Trapero, A., and D. Prusky,
5 *unpublished data*). These results argue for the importance of additional outreach and
6 additional research on the role of phenolic compounds in the resistance to olive
7 anthracnose.

8 Currently, screening tests of olive seedlings for anthracnose and cercosporiose are not
9 available. In the first case, adult plants are needed because the fruit is required for
10 inoculation (23,27), and in the second case, the latent period of cercosporiose is too long
11 to be applied in early screening (2). None of the new cultivars were classified as
12 resistant to *P. cladosporioides*. This lack of resistance could be due to the susceptibility
13 of the three genitors to the pathogen (2,26). In contrast, the effect of the cv. Frantoio in
14 conferring high resistance to *S. oleagina* and *C. acutatum* to its progeny was evident.
15 The additional high resistance of the cv. Frantoio to *Verticillium dahliae*, which is
16 considered the main soil-borne disease threatening olive production worldwide, makes
17 this cultivar especially valuable as a genitor in breeding programs (20,44). Other
18 resistant cultivars to *V. dahliae* (cvs. Changlot Real and Empeltre), *C. acutatum* (cv.
19 Koroneiki) and *S. oleagina* (cv. Lechín de Sevilla) are being used as genitors in the
20 olive breeding program of Córdoba (38).

21 Overall, the majority of the cultivars, especially the cv. UC-I 7-60, showed a good level
22 of resistance to the three pathogens, and remarkably, none of the cultivars were
23 susceptible to all three of the pathogens. This study also provides a helpful guideline for
24 the evaluation of olive cultivars and the main aerial pathogens of this crop. These results
25 of these tests are key points to consider prior to the release of any new cultivars into the
26 nursery industry.

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FIGURE LEGENDS

Fig. 1. Effect of olive genotype on the peacock spot severity (Disease Severity Index) of olive leaves that were inoculated with *Spilocaea oleagina* from naturally infected trees. The cvs. Arbequina (A), Frantoio (F), and Picual (P) were the genitors of the new genotypes. The bars represent the average of 120 leaves. For each genotype, the mean values with the letters a, b or c are significantly higher, equal, or lower, respectively, than the moderately susceptible control 'Arbequina' according to Dunnett's test at $P = 0.05$.

Fig. 2. Effect of olive genotype on the anthracnose severity (Area Under Disease Progress Curve) of olive fruit that were inoculated with *Colletotrichum acutatum*. The cultivars Arbequina (A), Frantoio (F), and Picual (P) were the genitors of the new genotypes. The bars represent the average of 150 fruits. For each genotype, the mean values with the letters a, b or c are significantly higher, equal, or lower, respectively, than the moderately susceptible control 'Arbequina' according to Dunnett's test at $P = 0.05$.

Fig. 4. Linear correlation between the incidence of leaves with peacock spot symptoms under field conditions and the disease severity of olive leaves that were inoculated with *Spilocaea oleagina*. The symbols represent 18 olive genotypes.

Fig. 3. Linear correlation between the incidence of olive fruit with anthracnose symptoms under field conditions and the disease severity (Area Under Disease Progress Curve) of fruits that were inoculated with *Colletotrichum acutatum*. The symbols represent 18 olive genotypes.

Fig. 5. Linear correlation between the total phenol content [mg gallic acid equivalent (GAE) kg^{-1} oil] of olive oil and the disease severity (Area Under Disease Progress Curve) of fruit that were inoculated with *Colletotrichum acutatum*. The symbols represent 12 olive genotypes.

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Figure 1.

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Figure 2.

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Figure 3.

Review

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Figure 4.

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Figure 5.

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Table 1. Incidence of peacock spot caused by *Spilocaea oleagina*, cercosporiose caused by *Pseudocercospora cladosporioides*, and anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum* spp. in three cultivars and 15 new cultivars of olive in an experimental orchard in southern Spain.

Genotype	Trees (N°)	Origin ^z	Disease										
			Peacock spot ^y					Cercosporiose				Anthracnose	
			2007	2008	2010	2011	Average	2007	2008	2010	2011	Average	2011
Arbequina	10		4.5b	1.3b	1.6b	3.1b	2.62	2.3b	2.4b	2.4b	2.2b	2.32	6.1b
Frantoio	10		0.1c	0.0c	0.0c	0.1c	0.05	4.1b	1.9b	4.8a	5.6a	4.10	0c
Picual	9		5.7b	0.8b	1.3b	3.9b	2.92	3.6b	0.7b	1.3b	2.4b	2.00	3.7c
Chiquitita	10		0.1c	0.0c	0.2c	0.1c	0.10	2.8b	2.6b	2.7b	2.8b	2.80	6.5b
UC-I 2-68	10		2.6c	0.1c	0.0c	0.2c	0.72	5.3a	3.3b	4.3b	5.9a	3.63	7.0b
UC-I 5-44	10	P × A	0.3c	0.0c	0.0c	0.2c	0.12	3.7b	4.1b	5.0a	5.9a	4.67	5.9b
UC-I 7-34	9		1.0c	0.0c	0.0c	0.2c	0.30	4.2b	2.7b	2.2b	4.5a	3.42	3.1c
UC-I 8-20	10		0.8c	0.0c	0.3b	0.0c	0.27	3.5b	0.9b	4.7a	5.5a	3.65	4.8b
UC-I 11-16	10		4.5b	0.4b	0.2c	1.6b	1.67	2.8b	1.5b	3.9b	4.7a	3.22	2.3c
UC-I 6-9	10		4.7b	0.9b	0.1c	1.3c	1.75	3.3b	1.9b	5.8a	5.3a	4.08	8.2b
UC-I 7-8	10	A × P	6.2b	0.8b	0.5b	2.3b	2.45	3.6b	3.7b	5.5a	5.7a	4.62	3.1c
UC-I 9-67	10		0.0c	0.0c	0.1c	0.3c	0.10	2.9b	2.4b	0.9b	1.8b	2.00	4.6b
UC-I 10-54	10		9.9a	6.2a	5.9a	9.4a	7.85	-	0.3b	3.2b	-	2.32	3.9b
UC-I 11-10	10		0.9c	0.3b	0.1c	0.0c	0.32	1.4b	1.6b	2.5b	4.1b	2.40	3.9b
UC-I 11-19	10		2.3c	0.2c	0.3c	1.0c	0.95	2.0b	0.8b	5.5a	5.0a	3.30	1.1c
UC-I 4-62	10	F × P	6.5a	1.1b	4.5a	6.9a	4.75	2.5b	1.0b	2.4b	3.4b	2.32	1.6c
UC-I 7-60	9		3.0b	0.1c	0.1c	1.4b	1.15	1.5b	0.6b	0.7b	4.0b	1.75	0.6c
UC-I 10-30	10		1.0c	0.1c	0.2c	0.3c	0.40	3.3b	3.3b	4.3b	6.2a	4.27	0c
Average				3.0	0.7	0.9	1.8		3.1	2.0	3.5	4.5	

^yThe leaf or fruit rot incidence was estimated using a 1-to-10 rating scale in which binary data (proportion of affected fruits) are normalized by applying the logit transformation of proportion (22). The scale values were directly subjected to an analysis of variance and mean comparison tests. For each year, the mean values with the letters a, b or c are significantly higher, equal, or lower, respectively, than the moderately susceptible control

^zArbequina^z according to Dunnett's test at $P = 0.05$.

^zThe new cultivars come from crosses between the cvs. Arbequina (A), Frantoio (F), and Picual (P).

Table 2. Relative susceptibility of 18 olive genotypes (3 traditional cultivars and 15 new cultivars) to peacock spot caused by *Spilocaea oleagina*, cercosporiose caused by *Pseudocercospora cladosporioides*, and anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum* spp.

Genotype	Trees (N ^o)	Origin ^w	Disease		
			Peacock spot ^x	Cercosporiose ^y	Anthracnose ^x
Arbequina	10		M ^z	M	M
Frantoio	10		R	S	R
Picual	9		S	M	R
Chiquitita	10		M-R	M	S-M
UC-I 2-68	10		M-R	S	S-M
UC-I 5-44	10	P × A	R	S	M-R
UC-I 7-34	9		M-R	S	R
UC-I 8-20	10		M-R	S	S-M
UC-I 11-16	10		M-R	S	M-R
UC-I 6-9	10		M-R	S	M
UC-I 7-8	10	A × P	M-R	S	M-R
UC-I 9-67	10		M-R	M	M
UC-I 10-54	10		S	M	M-R
UC-I 11-10	10		R	M	S-M
UC-I 1-19	10		R	S	R
UC-I 4-62	10	F × P	S-M	M	R
UC-I 7-60	9		R	M	R
UC-I 10-30	10		R	S	R

^wThe new cultivars come from crosses between the cvs. Arbequina (A), Frantoio (F), and Picual (P).

^xThe relative susceptibility according to the disease incidence in the field and the disease severity in artificial inoculation.

^yThe relative susceptibility according to disease incidence in the field.

^zThe disease reaction: susceptible (S), moderately susceptible (M), and resistant (R); the cultivars with different reactions under the controlled and field conditions show two letters.